

Synthesis and studies on copper(II) and lead(II) polyurethanes

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Metal-containing polyurethanes have been synthesized by the reaction of mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolinate-copper(II) with isophorone diisocyanate/toluene diisocyanate and mono(hydroxyethyl)phthalate-lead(II) with isophorone diisocyanate in DMF, and characterized by spectroscopic and thermal studies. The decomposition temperatures of these polymers were found to be significantly lower than those of metal-free polymers. However, the rates of decomposition of metal-containing polyurethanes were lower than those of polyurethanes having no metal atom.

The synthesis and studies on polyurethanes and metal containing polyurethanes is important since they find extensive applications in different industrial products. Polyurethanes based composite materials are applied in artificial cardiovascular devices owing to their favourable mechanical and antithrombogenic properties¹. A series of polyurethanes and other polymers containing different metal ions like Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have been reported². The synthesis of copolymers of polyurethanes with PMMA³, and application of polyurethanes as cationomers have been described. The phase separation occurring in polyurethane systems have also been studied⁵. The surface modifications of polyurethanes by plasma induced graft polymerisation of poly(ethylene glycol)methacrylate has been described⁶. Thermal studies⁷ on the copolymers of polyurethane (PU) with poly(caprolactone-g-PMMA) indicated that the phase separation of polycaprolactone and PMMA was incomplete. The synthesis of PU from cashew-nut shell liquid has also been reported⁸.

The present report describes the synthesis of copper(II) containing polyurethanes derived from mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolinate (HEQ) and toluene diisocyanate (TDI) isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), and lead(II) containing polyurethanes derived from mono(hydroxyethyl)phthalate (HEP) and isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI).

Results and Discussion

Quinolinic anhydride was prepared by the reaction of quinolinic acid and acetic anhydride and characterised by its spectra. Cupric salts of mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolinate was synthesized from quinolinic anhydride, ethylene glycol and copper acetate. Similarly lead salt of mono(hydroxyethyl)phthalate was synthesized from phthalic anhydride, ethylene glycol and lead acetate. $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2$ were found to be insoluble in most of the organic solvents. Polymerization involving these salts was done in DMF as it is a good solvent for polyurethanes⁹. The solubility of these compounds in polar solvents like

DMF and DMSO is quite high.

The polymerization reaction was carried out by the gradual addition (1 h) of the diisocyanate dissolved in DMF to the stirred solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2/\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2$ in the same solvent at room temperature in nitrogen atmosphere. The details of the preparation of polyurethane from TDI and IPDI are shown in Table 1. These polyurethanes are soluble in polar solvents like DMSO and DMF and are insoluble in other organic solvents like carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene. The structures of the metal containing polyurethanes from $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}]$ and $[\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ are presented in Chart 1.

Chart 1

The *in situ* synthesis of metal containing polymers was achieved by the reaction of Cu^{II} -mono(hydroxyethyl)-quinolinolate with either 2,4-toluene diisocyanate or isophorone diisocyanate, and Pb^{II} -mono(hydroxyethyl)-phthalate with isophorone diisocyanate. The resulting products $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-DI}]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ and $[\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ were found insoluble in most of the organic solvents. The synthetic conditions and the physical properties of these compounds are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Reaction conditions and physical properties of polyurethanes

Compd.	Yield %	Colour	Solubility	η^* g cm^{-2}
$\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}$	78	White	DMF, DMSO	0.61
$\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-IPDI}$	72	Brown	DMF, DMSO	0.56
$\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}$	74	Green	DMF, DMSO	0.53

*Determined at a concentration of 0.05 g ml^{-1} in DMSO at 30° .

The intrinsic viscosity of the polymers measured by Ubbelohde viscometer indicates that they have very low values (Table 1) when compared to analogous polymers. This may be attributed to the fact that polar solvent like DMSO facilitates the truncation of polymer chain resulting in the formation of low molecular weight species.

The ir spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2$ respectively exhibited bands at 3500 cm^{-1} (OH) group and peaks at 1730 (C=O) and 1585 cm^{-1} (carboxylate).

The ir spectra of the metal-containing polyurethanes showed appreciable changes in their spectral pattern when compared to the free polyurethanes. The metal containing polyurethanes exhibited bands at 3350 (NH) and at $1730\text{--}1760$, $1560\text{--}1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (carboxyl). The bands at $1560\text{--}1610$ and 1400 cm^{-1} confirm the presence of ionic links in the polyurethanes¹⁰.

Thermal stability of polyurethanes :

Figs.1 and 2 show the TGA curves of the polyurethanes $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}]$ $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ $[\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ and the free polymers (Table 2). The initial decomposition

Fig. 1. TGA curves of (A) Cu salt of HEQ, (B) polyurethane from $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ and IPDI and (C) polyurethane from $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ and TDI.

temperature (IDT) of Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} systems indicate that the precursor salts have higher IDT compared to the corresponding metal-containing polyurethanes. The $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ has an IDT of 187° , while the corresponding metal contain-

ing polyurethanes $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-IPDI}]$ exhibited the decomposition temperature at 156° and 167° respectively. Similarly, in case of the Pb system, the decomposition temperature was found to be 193° for $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2$ and 163° for $[\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}]$. The trend observed in the temperature corresponding to different weight percentage loss also follows the same pattern.

It has been reported¹¹ that the thermal degradation of polyurethanes normally starts via urethane scission leading

Fig. 2. TGA curves of (A) Pb salt of HEP and (B) polyurethane from $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}$.

to isocyanate and hydroxyl components. Durairaj and Rao² reported that 10% weight-loss for $[\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-TDI}]$ polyurethanes occurs at 197° . In the present system, however, the 10% weight-loss occurred for $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}$ at a higher temperature. This is due to the fact that $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-TDI}$ polymer has purely ionic links in the metal-containing part, but $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2\text{-TDI}$ has the configuration of a tetracoordination complex in their metal-containing part which requires a higher temperature for breakdown. In the case of $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2$ the first stage of decomposition occurs at $193\text{--}230^\circ$ and $230\text{--}290^\circ$ which corresponds to 14% weight-loss. This may be attributed to the loss of two glycol groups. In the second stage of decomposition, nearly 27% weight-loss occurs at $289\text{--}276^\circ$, which may be due to the scission of phthalic acid group. The third stage of decomposition that occurs at $376\text{--}496^\circ$ can be attributed to the loss of CO_2 and CO in the subsequent step. The final residue is due to the formation of PbO . The polyurethanes from $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}$ contained purely ionic links in the metal-containing part and hence are liable to breakdown at these points during processing, thus reducing the melt viscosity and increasing the ease of processability. Polyurethanes from $\text{Cu}(\text{HEQ})_2$ and IPDI have a tetracoordinate complex in their system and require higher temperature for breakdown of those points resulting in lowering of molecular weight and melt viscosity. However, because of the comparatively higher stability of the complex structures with Cu^{2+} ions, electrical conductivity and insulating properties of the polyurethanes containing Cu^{2+} may be different from $\text{Pb}(\text{HEP})_2\text{-IPDI}$ polyurethanes.

Table 2. TGA data of polyurethanes

Compd.	IDT °C	% Weight-loss at different temperatures (°C)			
		10	25	50	75
Cu(HEQ) ₂	187	246	285	334	426
Cu(HEQ) ₂ -TDI	156	215	257	309	390
Cu(HEQ) ₂ -IPDI	167	198	233	312	478
Pb(HEP) ₂	193	250	367	425	—
Pb(HEP) ₂ -IPDI	163	242	282	288	450

Experimental

Quinolinic anhydride : A mixture of quinolinic acid (6.7 g, 0.1 mol) and acetic anhydride (18.5 ml, 0.2 mol) was heated to gentle boiling until the solution became clear and the heating continued for 10 min and then cooled. The crystalline mass obtained was ground and filtered. The crystals were again ground with dry ether (15 ml) and filtered. The product was washed with dry ether, dried in air at 100° and crystallized from benzene, (72%).

Cupric mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolate, [Cu(HEQ)₂] : To ethylene glycol (28.89 ml, 0.4 mol), was added quinolinic anhydride (14.9 g, 0.1 mol) with stirring at 95–110° for 45 min. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at the same temperature and copper(II) acetate (9.95 g, 0.05 mol) was then added to the hot reaction mixture. The stirring was continued for 45 min at the same temperature and the resulting solid was washed with acetone followed by dilute acetic acid and acetone (to remove unreacted acetate), and dried in vacuum at 70°, (68%).

Metal-containing polyurethanes : Cu(HEQ)₂-TDI polyurethanes : To a mixture of monomer complex cupric(II) mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolate (4.83 g, 0.01 mol), DMF (10 ml) and di-n-butyltindilaurate (0.16 g), toluene diisocyanate (15.62 g) dissolved in DMF (7 ml) was slowly (1 h) added under a stream of nitrogen gas at room temperature. The stirring was continued for another hour and the temperature of the reaction mixture was raised at first to 90° and then to 110° with constant stirring. After keeping overnight, DMF was added in excess, filtered and the filtrate was poured into cold water to precipitate the polymer. The product was filtered, washed several times with chloroform and dried in vacuum at 80°, (78%).

Cu(HEQ)₂-IPDI polyurethanes : To the mixture containing monomer complex cupric(II) mono(hydroxyethyl)quinolate (4.83 g), DMF (10 ml) and di-n-butyltindilaurate (0.166 g), isophorone diisocyanate (2.30 ml) dissolved in DMF (7 ml) was added. The previous procedure for synthesis was also adopted for synthesis of this product,

(72%).

Lead mono(hydroxyethyl)phthalate : [Pb(HEP)₂] : To ethylene glycol (64 ml, 1 mol), phthalic anhydride (37 g, 0.25 mol) was added slowly with stirring at 85–90° for 3 h and then Pb(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O (41 g, 0.125 mol) was added to the hot reaction mixture. The product separated out and was dried in air, (72%).

Pb(HEP)₂-IPDI polyurethanes : Isophorone diisocyanate (2.3 ml, 0.165 mol) dissolved in DMF (10 ml) was slowly added (with stirring under a stream of nitrogen for 30 min) to a mixture containing Pb(HEP)₂ (9.38 g, 0.015 mol), DMF (15 ml) and di-n-butyltindilaurate (0.25 g). The mixture was stirred continuously for 1 h. Then the temperature of the reaction mixture was raised first to 80° and then to 110° with continuous stirring for 30 min at each temperature. DMF was added in excess to this mixture, filtered, and the filtrate poured into cold water to precipitate the polymer. The product was filtered, washed several times with CHCl₃ and dried in vacuum at 80°, (74%).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Hitachi 270–50 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Mettler TA 1000 instrument in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 20°/min. The elemental analysis was carried out on a Coleman C-H-N analyzer.

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